

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2
0
2
4

No 4

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil **IQTISODIYOT** **TARAQQIYOT** va

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Elektron nashr. 980 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 30-aprelda ruxsat etildi.

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU YoMMMIB birinchi prorektori
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalendarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., "O'IRIAM" ilmiy tadqiqot markazi direktori – prorektor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TMI professori
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professori
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d. TDIU professori
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., profesor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d., "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d., TAQU katta o'qituvchisi
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi iqtisodiy jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti bo'limi boshlig'i
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

MUNDARIJA

Organizational Behavior and Leadership.....	10
Ibrokhim Gulomov	
Baliqchilikda klasterlarni tashkil etishning nazariy asoslari.....	18
Olim Murtazayev, Muydinov Olim Bekmurotovich	
Оценка состояния привлечения инвестиций в сферу туризма Узбекистана и механизмы управления	24
Арзиматов Бобирмирзо Зокирджон угли	
Biologik aktivlar buxgalteriya hisobni milliy va xalqaro standartlarga muvofiq takomillashtirish masalalari...27	
Axmadaliyeva Zebo Abduxalimovna	
Aholi yashash joylarida yong'in risklarini bartaraf etish xizmatlardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	32
Aziz Zikriyoev	
O'zbekistonda ilmiy darajali kadrlar tayyorlash tizimi boshqaruvining tashkiliy tuzilmasi va vazifalari.....	40
Beknaeva Shaxnoza Vladimirovna	
Mintaqaviy turizmning iqtisodiyot rivojlanishiga ta'siri (O'zbekiston turistik xizmatlar bozori misolida).....	45
D. B. O'roqova	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini ko'paytirishning asosiy yo'llari.....	50
Ibrohimov Boburmirzo Baxtiyor o'g'li, Sayfiddinov Sarvarbek Anvarbek o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalarining aksiyalar bozorida faoliyati tahlili: muammolar va yechimlar	55
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
Qurilishda modernizatsiya va diversifikatsiya qilish asosida yangi ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarini oshirish	63
Islamov Ozodjon	
Sanoat korxonalarini innovatsion salohiyatini oshirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	67
J. K. Boymurodov	
Mamlakatda yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	72
Kadirxodjayeva Nilufar Raxmatullayevna	
BlokchEYn texnologiyalari yordamida raqamli iqtisodiyotni o'zgartirish	77
Karabayev Rustam Zafarovich, Saitkamolov Muxammadxo'ja Sobirxo'ja o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida zamonaviy mehnat bozorining rivojlanishi	84
Layli Mirzayeva	
Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirishda investitsion resurslardan samarali foydalanish mexanizmlari.....	88
Luiza Komilovna Xaydarova	
Umumta'lim muassasalari sonining ekonometrik tahlilini pedagogik metodlar yordamida amalga oshirish....	93
Ravshanova Muhayyo Maxmanazarovna	
O'zbekiston tarixiy shaharlarida turistik faoliyati shakllanishi va ularni boshqarishning nazariy asoslari.....	98
Meliqulov G'ayrat Abdug'afforovich	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish va ilmiy tadqiqot rivojlanishining havo ifloslanish darajasiga ta'siri	105
Murodullayev Kamoliddin Sherzod o'g'li, Sadibekova Bibisora Djapparovna, Turdiqulov Farrux Ravshanjon o'g'li	
Hududlarni rivojlantirish va "yashil iqtisodiyot"ni shakllantirishning ekologik muammolari.....	110
Maxkamov Saidafzal Saidkamol o'g'li, Yigitaliyeva Dilnavo Mansurjon qizi	
Ekoturizm obyektining tasniflanishi va alohida xususiyatlari	116
Qodirov Azizjon Anvarovich	
Mamlakatimiz oliy ta'lim tizimida sifat menejmentidan foydalanishning konseptual asoslari	121
Saidqulova Furuza Farmonovna	
Bo'lajak iqtisodchilarning kasbiy kompetensiyalari.....	125
Shukurova Marifat Xodjiakbar qizi	
Ta'limning bosqichlari va ularning inson kapitalini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati	129
To'rayeva Hurriyat To'yqulovna	
Hududlarda to'g'ridan to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish dasturini amalga oshirishda marketingni rivojlantirish yo'llari	136
Xamidov O. X., Tojiyeva A. F.	
Investitsiyalar marketingining strategik aspektlari.....	143
Xodjamberdiyeva Dilnoza Bahtiyorovna	
Xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishda investitsion muhit jozibadorligini oshirishga nazariy qarashlar	149
A. Bektemirov, A. A. Abdurahmonov	
Qishloq xo'jaligi raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning ilg'or xorij tajribasi.....	154
Abdulloyev Asliddin Junaydullayevich, Ochilov Narzullo Fayzulloyevich	
Sanoat ishlab chiqarish tizimining investitsion xususiyatlari.....	159
Yodgorova Xalima To'liqinovna	
Turizm sohasi uchun yuqori malakali kadrlarni tayyorlashda davlat va xususiy sherikchilikning o'zaro bog'liqligi tahlili.....	165
Raxmatov Adxam Itolmasovich	

Mamlakatimizda turizm tashkilotlari faoliyatini qoʻllab-quvvatlash maqsadida marketing instrumentlari orqali samarali tizim yaratish.....	169
Suyunova Kamilla Baxromovna	
Qishloq xoʻjaligida agrokimyo xizmatlar koʻrsatishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yoʻllari	173
Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotga investitsiyalarni jalb qilishni faollashtirish muammolari.....	178
Xomitov K. Z., Masharipova S. R.	
Considerations on the Problem of Illegal Migration and Human Trafficking	183
Azamatova Gulmira Bayirbekovna, Otarbayeva Guljan Kobeyevna	
Sustainable Development and Environmental Economics in Uzbekistan: A Focus on Carbon Pricing and Renewable Energy	186
Muhammadiyev Poʻlatjon Ilhomjon oʻgʻli, Urganbayeva Dilnoza Toxtasinovna	
The use of Digital Technologies in the Provision Of Utilities to the Population	192
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich, Inoyatova Durdona Shoxaydarovna, Alijonov Jamshid Alijon oʻgʻli	
The Current State of the Digital Economy in the Agrarian Sphere: Problems and Solutions	196
Babadjanov Abdirashid Musayevich	
Behavioral Theory of the Firm.....	201
Egamberdieva Oydin Abror qizi	
The Role of Information Technologies in Increasing the Capitalization of Commercial Banks	207
Egamova Makhfurat Esanovna	
Финансовые риски в исламском финансировании для внедрения в Республики Узбекистан	211
Абдуллоев Фуркат Олимджонович	
Совершенствование методологии экспертизы инвестиционных проектов	216
Бекимбетова Гулнора Маратовна	
Методические подходы к формированию механизмов стратегического управления развитием химической отрасли.....	223
Бибутова Шахло Саъдуллаевна	
Меры по снижению доли теневой экономики в стране.....	228
Махмудова Юлдузхон Бахромжон кизи, Сафаров Гиёсиддин Абдуллаевич ўгли	
Формирование национальной инновационной системы – одна из приоритетных задач повышения конкурентоспособности Республики Узбекистан	232
Н. М. Махмудов, А. А. Алиев, З. А. Мирзоев	
Мониторинг и анализ современного состояния и развития промышленности в Узбекистане.....	237
Назарова Раъно Рустамовна, Исмоилова Малика Дилшодовна	
Цифровая платформа как инструмент трансформации бизнес-процессов.....	243
Раупов Жамшид Рашидович	
Роль применения ключевых показателей эффективности труда на предприятиях.....	249
Рахматуллаева Шахноза Хамидовна	
Влияние цифровой трансформации на инвестиционную привлекательность Узбекистана.....	255
Сайткамолов Мухаммадхожа Сабириходжа угли, Маркабаева Жансая Айбек кызы	
Организация и координация методической помощи при управлении педагогическими кадрами	261
Хакимова Майя Юрьевна	
Интеграция узбекистана в мировое экономическое содружество путем унификации бухгалтерского учета на основе МСФО	266
Зарипова Саёхат Зафаровна	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan investitsiya loyihalarini moliyalashni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari.....	271
Abduqodirova Ozoda Anvarjon qizi	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan jismoniy shaxslarga ajratilgan kreditlarning joriy tahlili.....	276
Abdusalomov Jaxongir Oʻktam oʻgʻli	
Globalashuv sharoitida mamlakatimizda sugʻurta bozorini raqamlashtirishning ahamiyati.....	282
Anvarova Z.	
The Role of Parents and Teachers in Promoting a Healthy Lifestyle in Children	286
Axtamov Djamshed Baxromovich	
A Study of the Importance of Green Economy in Uzbekistan Sustainable Economic Development and its Measurement Indicators in Relation to Environment.....	291
Ataniyazova Maksuda Baltayevna, Tairova Zarnigor Mammot qizi	
Konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobot tuzishning zarurligi.....	296
Avazov Ilxom Ravshanovich	
Foydani soliqqa tortish obyektini sifatidagi iqtisodiy tarkibi.....	301
Axrorov Zarif Oripovich	
Surxondaryo viloyatida aholining uy-joy bilan taʼminlanganlik darajasini tahlili.....	309
Ibragimov Qobil Toʻxtamishovich	
Review of Methodological Approaches to Enterprises Financial Condition Analysis.....	314
Ismailova Maxbuba Mirxalilovna	

Innovatsion rivojlanish sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini tasniflanishining nazariy va ilmiy asoslari.....	319
Masharipova Manzura Alimbayevna	
Korxonalarda benchmarking strategiyalarini qo'llashning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari.....	325
Narziyeva Dilafiruz Muxtorovna	
Davlat budjetining soliqsiz daromadlari shakllanishini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	330
O'ktamova Nargiza Narzulla qizi	
Mamlakatimizda sanoat ishlab chiqarishi korxonalarining rivojlanish holati tahlili.....	334
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li	
Moliyaviy natijalar to'g'risidagi hisobotni moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlar talablari asosida tuzish.....	339
Pardayeva Zulfizar Alimovna	
Raqamlashtirish sharoitida qo'shma korxonasi faoliyatining tahlili.....	343
Rashidov Jamshid Xamidovich	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning rivojlanishida oilaviy tadbirkorlikning o'rni.....	348
Raximov Baxromjon Ibroximovich, Saloxiddinov Zuxriddin Nuriddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatishning ilmiy asoslari.....	352
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida telekommunikatsiya sohasini rivojlantirish ilmiy asoslari.....	356
Toshmatov Salohiddin Zayniddinovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida innovatsiyalarni joriy etishning huquqiy masalalari.....	360
Turg'unov Saloxiddin Jamol o'g'li, Mirzayeva Mohidil Vohidovna	
Zamonaviy sharoitlarda korxonalarining moliyaviy baqarorligini yaxshilash masalalari.....	366
Usmanova Guljahon Ulug'bek qizi	
Franshizalarni jalb qilishda davlat boshqaruvi tizimida marketing tadqiqotlarining ahamiyati.....	371
Xodjayev Anvar Rasulovich	
Transport Decarbonization Strategy.....	377
Yarashova Vasila Kamalovna, Muradov Bekzod Xidirnazar ugli	
Temir yo'l transportida ishlab chiqarish faoliyatining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish.....	382
Yermatova Dilnoza Axmadjonovna	
Iqtisodiyotda davlat ishtirokini qisqartirish va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	387
Yuldashev Xusniddin Abdullayevich	
Iссиqlik ta'minoti xizmatlarini ko'rsatish samaradorligi va sifatini baholash ko'rsatkichlari tizimi.....	390
Abdulaziz Abdumo'minovich Matro'ziyev	
Iссиqlik ta'minoti xizmatlari sifatiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar va ularni baholash.....	394
Abdulaziz Abdumo'minovich Matro'ziyev	
Jismoniy shaxslarning mol-mulkiga soliq solishni takomillashtirish.....	399
Abdullayev Zafarjon Alijonovich, Zaydullayev Abduhabib Boliqul o'g'li	
Sug'urta tashkilotlarida hisob siyosatini ishlab chiqishning ahamiyati.....	404
Abduraimova Maftunaxon Axmatovna	
Bank risklarini boshqarishning xalqaro tajribalari.....	409
Abdurasulov Jaxongir Abduvaliyevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari ijtimoiy ma'sulligini ta'minlash mexanizmining amal qilish darajasi.....	416
Bayisbayev Javlon Nurlanovich	
Qishloq aholisining qishloq xo'jaligida bilim va innovatsiyalarni o'zlashtirishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni iqtisodiy baholash (Samarqand viloyati misolida).....	421
Bozorova Lobar Nuralevna	
Направления совершенствования инновационных стратегий в деятельности промышленных предприятий.....	427
Дониерова Зухрабону Алишер кизи	
Mol-mulk solig'ining korxonalar faoliyatiga ta'siri.....	432
Qudiyarov Kishibay Ramatullayevich	
Banklar reytingini aniqlash va barqarorligini ta'minlashning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	438
Maxmudov Omon Tuxtayevich	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida tijorat banklarining aktiv va passiv operatsiyalarini innovatsion usullar orqali boshqarishni takomillashtirish.....	442
Mo'minova Ma'suda Baxtiyarovna	
Auditorlik tekshiruvini dasturiy ta'minot asosida tashkil etish: muammo va yechimlar.....	447
Nazarova Kamola Sattorali qizi	
Ishlab chiqarish infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishning davlat tomonidan tartibga solish konsepsiyasi.....	453
Normurodov Xusan Eshmaxmatovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning ahamiyati hamda uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	460
Nurullayeva Shaxnoza, Saydullayeva Saodat	

Tijorat banklari inson kapitali samaradorligini baholashda KPI ko'rsatkichlaridan foydalanish mexanizmlari.....	467
Turaeva Mastura Kurbanovna	
Сущность и особенности инвестиционно-строительного процесса.....	471
А. Бектемиров, Б.М.Абдувалиев	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlarni boshqarishning dolzarb masalalari.....	478
Saidov Hayotjon Raxmatulloyevich	
Tijorat banklarida kredit operatsiyalari hisobini takomillashtirish.....	482
Sa'dullayeva Asalxon Muzaffarovna	
Ko'p tarmoqli fermer xo'jaliklarining raqobatbardoshlikni baholash usullari.....	485
Abdulloyev Asliddin Junaydullayevich, Teshayev Mirolim Djumayevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarida soliq yukini optimallashtirish mexanizmi.....	490
To'xsanov Qudratillo Nozimovich	
Davlat sektorida ichki audit tadbirlarini umumiy rejalashtirish.....	495
Xamidova Z. U.	
Aholi moliyaviy savodxonligini oshirish va uning ahamiyati.....	501
Xudayarova Xurshida Abdunazarovna	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	505
Xudoyberdiyev Jamshid Juraboy o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida buxgalteriya hisobi va ichki auditni takomillashtirish.....	511
Shaymatova Nargiza Ashurovna	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida sug'urta xizmatlari.....	516
Shodmonova Odina G'ofur qizi	
Fuqarolar davlat pensiya ta'minoti tizimining amaldagi holati tahlili.....	520
Sholdarov Dilshod Azimiddin o'g'li	
Aholiga bank xizmatlari ko'rsatishning ijtimoiy ahamiyati.....	525
Eldor Uskanov	
Innovatsion boshqaruvning ilg'or xorijiy tajribalari.....	530
Yusupova Jamila Karamatdinovna	
Neft-gaz korxonalarini moliyaviy-iqtisodiy faoliyati natijalari tahlili ("O'ZBEKNEFTGAZ" AJ misolida).....	534
Umurzoqov Jamoliddin Sherbekovich	
Korxonalarda savdo marketing faoliyati samaradorligini baholash.....	541
Sobirov Azizbek Avzbekovich	
Moliyaviy firibgarliklarga qarshi kurashishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	548
Gadaev Ismat Yadgarovich	
Hududlarda islom iqtisodiyoti tamoyillari asosida amalga oshirilgan investitsion loyihalar: to'siqlar va yechimlar.....	551
Irgasheva Gulbahor Sodiqovna	
O'zbekistonda investitsiyalardan samarali foydalanish asosida oziq-ovqat sanoati samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	554
Kobilova Nasiba Xurramovna	
Foreign Economic Relations as a Factor of Effective Functioning of the Economy.....	561
Bakhodurova Sulkhiya Azizkhodjaevna, Li Marina Rudolfovna, Mukhtarova Donata Ravshanbekovna, Romashkin Roman Anatolyevich	
Modern Approaches to the Organization and Development of the Consumer Services Market.....	566
Musyeva Shoirazimovna	
Ishlab chiqarish siklini qisqartirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	570
Odina Nabiyevna Tuychiyeva, Nazarova Latofat Toirjon qizi	
Asalarichilik mahsulotlari bozorida marketing strategiyasini amalga oshirish.....	575
Rashidova Xadicha Tursunalievna	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida bank faoliyatini iqtisodiy-matematik modellashtirish yo'llari.....	581
Raxmanov Mexridin Sindarovich	
Korporativ boshqaruv amaliyoti bo'yicha hisobot tuzish bo'yicha xorijiy tajriba.....	586
Tashmatov Rustam Xusanovich	
Iqtisodiyotda davlat ishtirokini qisqartirish va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	592
Yuldashev Xusniddin Abdullayevich	
Iqtisodiyotda turizm o'rnini statistik baholash uslubiyoti.....	595
Zilola Jumanova	
Финансовые риски в исламском финансировании для внедрения в Республики Узбекистан.....	602
Абдуллоев Фуркат Олимджонович	
Блокчейн-технология и информационная безопасность в цифровой экономике Узбекистана.....	607
Кадилов Алишер Исмаилович	
Цифровая платформа как инструмент трансформации бизнес-процессов.....	611
Раупов Жамшид Рашидович	

O'zbekistonda zamonaviy kabel va sim mahsulotlari ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalar faoliyatiga nazar.....	617
Rashidova Odina Olimjon qizi	
Современные тенденции развития валютных отношений в Узбекистане.....	622
Камалов Камолатдин Кахрамонович	
Sug'urta sohasining O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotidagi o'рни.....	626
Sharobiddinov Akramjon Goyibbayevich	
Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi va undan O'zbekistonda foydalanish yo'nalishlari.....	630
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
Modeling the Stackelberg strategy in a linear model (linear city) Hotteling.....	635
Musayeva Shaira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
Mulkning kapitallashuvi darajasini iqtisodiy jihatdan amalga oshirish samaradorligini baholash uslublari.....	644
Norboyev Odil Abrayevich	
Tijorat banklarining kredit portfelini amaliy holati va ekonometrik tahlillari: ATB "Aloqabank" misolida.....	649
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich, Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
O'zbekistonda "yashil iqtisodiyot" muhitida kreditlash va moliyalashtirish imkoniyatlari.....	654
Taxir Urkinbayev	
Budjet tashkilotlarida ichki nazorat tizimini tashkil qilishning xususiyatlari.....	658
Abduraxmanov Ramazon Abdullayevich	
Chinese Commercial Banks Experience in Asset Diversification.....	663
Uktamova Nozima Narzulla kizi	
Sanoat taraqqiyotida ishlab chiqarish korxonalarini ustuvor rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	667
Yadgarov Akram Akbarovich	
Анализ деятельности коммерческих банков Узбекистана по кредитованию физических лиц.....	673
Базарова Нигора Равшановна	
Mahalliy va xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishning innovatsion jarayonlarga ta'sirini baholash.....	684
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida innovatsiyalarning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	689
Kuziyeva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Xusanov Faxriddin Jamoliddin o'g'li	
Tashqi mehnat migratsiyasi.....	694
O. N. Djurayev	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda sanoat tarmog'ining davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanishini baholash.....	699
Otaboyeva Dildora	
Nobank kredit tashkilotlarining moliyaviy xizmatlari sifatini oshirishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	705
Raimov Xurshid Muxtorovich	
Tijorat banklarida moliyaviy injiniringni qo'llash istiqbollari.....	711
Saipnazarov Sherbek Shaylavbekovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi moliya bozorida tijorat banklari faoliyati: muammo va yechimlar.....	716
Toymuxamedov Ibroxim Rixsiboevich, Jumaev Islombek Akram o'g'li	
Agrar ta'lim tizimida boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	723
Boltayev Nurali Shiramatovich, Beglayev Uchqun Xurramovich, Abdiyev Izzat Risqiboyevich	
O'zini o'zi band qilgan shaxslardan olinadigan soliqlarni takomillashtirish orqali yashirin iqtisodiyotni jilovlash masalalari.....	731
Davranov Iskandar Jumayevich	
Iqtisodiy konsentratsiyalarni tartibga solish va nazorat qilishni takomillashtirish.....	738
Luqmanov Sharifxon A'zam o'g'li	
Role of Private and Public Kindergartens in Early Childhood Development.....	744
Makhmudova Munisakhon Abbos qizi	
"Yashil" enegriya quvvatlarini barpo etish iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlash asosi sifatida.....	749
Muminova Elnoraxon Abdukarimovna, Umarova Dilnoza Oybek qizi	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda CVP-tahlilni tashkil etishning muammoli jihatlari.....	754
Qlichev Baxtiyor Pardayevich	
Korxonada likvidlik riskini minimallashtirish orqali uning moliyaviy barqarorligini saqlab qolish.....	759
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
Развитие международных торгово-экономических связей Республики Узбекистан.....	766
Ким Татьяна Валерьевна, Гофуржонова Шахрибону Бахромжон кизи	
Kapital qurilishni boshqarish samaradorligini oshirishning dolzarb masalalari.....	774
A. Bektemirov, M. U. Sarimsoqov	
O'zbekiston mehnat bozorida yoshlarning ish bilan bandlik darajasini oshirish.....	780
Mambetjanov Qahramon Qurbandurdiyevich, Bahromov Shahzod Fazliddinovich	
Роль имиджа в улучшении инвестиционной привлекательности высших учебных заведений.....	787
Жанзаков Бекзот, Жонузоков Мирзабек	
Innovatsion kichik tadbirkorlikni qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha xorij tajribasi va uni mamlakat iqtisodiyotida qo'llash imkoniyati.....	795
Toshaliyeva Saodat Toxirovna, Eshqulova Dilorom Abduravupovna	

Перспективы развития банковского сектора в Узбекистане для иностранных туристов802 Муминов Шахзод Низомиддинович, Каримова Азиза Махомадризовна	802
Innovatsion faoliyat moliyaviy modellari va mexanizmlarini rivojlantirishning konseptual asoslari806 Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna	806
Qishloq xo'jaligi tarmoqlarini innovatsion rivojlantirish bo'yicha xorijiy tajribalar va ulardan respublikamizda samarali foydalanish yo'llari814 Ishniyazov Baxrom Normamatovich	814
Turistik xizmatlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va marketing tadqiqotlari819 Berdiqulova Iroda Rayimqulovna	819
Qoraqalpog'iston qishloq xo'jaligi: asosiy muammolar va rivojlanishining ustuvor yo'nalishlari823 Yeshimbetov Uktamjon Xudaybergenovich	823
Iqtisodiyotning erkinlashtirilishi sharoitlarida kichik biznes sektori rivojlanishining imkoniyatlari.....832 Botirova R. A., Sirojiddinov I. Q.	832
Kriptovalyuta va blokcheyn tadqiqotlari: tendensiyalar va istiqbollar835 Berdikulov Jurabek	835
Bank risklarni monitoring qilish tizimini takomillashtirish837 Hamroyev Sherzod Axtamovich	837
O'zbekiston hududlariga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda ko'p qavatli "yashil" fermer xo'jaliklarini tashkil etishning ahamiyati843 Turdimuratova Aziza Alisherovna	843
Surxondaryo viloyatining mahalliy budjet daromadlarini oshirish yo'llari va uni arima modeli asosida prognozlash.....846 Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norqo'chqor qizi	846
Qishloq xo'jaligi tarmog'ining mamlakat iqtisodiyotidagi o'rni va undagi tarkibiy o'zgarishlarni statistik baholash.....856 Zakirova Umida Maxamadaminovna	856
O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mohiyati863 Pardayev Jamshid Muzaffarovich	863
Turizm bozorini rivojlantirishda mehnat bozorining tutgan o'rni va ahamiyati872 Berdiqulova Iroda Rayimqulovna, Berdikulov Jurabek	872
Проблемы расчета определения и планирования прибыли предприятий в условиях модернизации экономики876 Алиева С. С.	876
Роль применения информационных технологий "BLOCKCHAIN" в совершенствовании системы бухгалтерского учета Республики Узбекистан.....881 Холбеков Расул Олимович	881
Sanatoriy-sog'lomlashtirish muassasasida ichki audit qanday amalga oshiriladi: usullari886 Shafkarov Faxriddin Xudayberdievich	886
Tashqi savdo operatsiyalarining yagona elektron axborot tizimida umidsiz qarzdorlik masalasi892 Tashmuxeimov Dilmirod Mirabzalovich	892
Принципы формирования отчета о финансовых результатах в национальной и зарубежной практике897 Эргашева Шахло Тургуновна	897
Xalqaro raqamli integratsiyaning O'zbekiston an'anaviy banklarning raqobat muhitiga ta'siri907 Abdujabbarov Abdurasul Abdurashid o'g'li	907
O'zbekistonda turizm sohasida kadrlar tayyorlash tizimini takomillashtirish: muammolar va strategiyalar....915 Eshmurodov Rustam Sayfiddin o'g'li	915
Yoshlar turizmini rivojlantirishda ommaviy va alternativ turizmning o'rni hamda volontyorlikning hususiyatlari.....918 Allayor Norboyev Ismoilovich	918
Parrandachilik statistikasi ko'rsatkichlar tizimini shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari.....922 Bobomuratov Imomqul Islamovich	922
Iqtisodiyotda kambag'allik darajasini qisqartirishda moliya bozori instrumentlaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....927 Shaxnoza Qobilova	927
Sohibqiron Amir Temur va Adam Smitning soliqlarga bo'lgan qarashlarining xususiyatlari to'g'risidagi fikrlar932 Alimov Ilxomjon Ikromovich	932
O'zbekiston Respublikasida zamonaviy bank xizmatlarinin rivojlantirish istiqbollari (O'ZMILLIYBANK AJ misolida)938 Kadirov Laziz	938
Milliy barqaror rivojlanish sohasidagi maqsad va vazifalarni amalga oshirishda iqtisodiy indikatorlar tahlili .941 Xoshimov Sobir Murtazayevich	941

The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Digital Transformation.....	945
Raimjonova Madina Asrarovna	
Tadbirkorlikda innovatsion faoliyatni moliyalashtirish masalalari	949
Otaxanov Sardorbek Maxammadali o'g'li	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyati samarasini oshirishda iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning strategik yo'nalishlari	952
I. M. Kamoliddinov, Sodiqov Maqsudjon Abduolimovich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarini soliq mexanizmi orqali rivojlantirish masalalari.....	955
Akbarov Akramjon Ibroximjonovich	
Yashil investitsiya samaradorligini oshirish masalalari.....	959
Ibrohimov Muhammadjon Abdullajanovich	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarini rivojlantirish va eksport imkoniyatlarini oshirish yo'llari	962
K. M. Umarkulov	
“Yashil” iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda tadbirkorlik faoliyati va uning hissasini oshirish masalalari	966
G. T. Mamajanova	
Kichik biznes faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlashda mahalliy boshqaruv bilan mushtarak jihatlarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	970
Ubaydullayev Akmal Tulkinboyevich	
Aholini ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlashning tashkiliy-huquqiy asoslarini takomillashtirish masalalari.....	976
Tursunov Abdulla Qoraboshevich	

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Raimjonova Madina Asrarovna

Professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Abstract: The article examines the opinions of the world's leading scientists on the role and characteristics of artificial intelligence in digital transformation, development in the field of artificial intelligence trends were analyzed, the main directions of work in the field of artificial intelligence in different countries of the world, justified conclusions and proposals were developed on the role of artificial intelligence in the transformation, and recommendations were given for its application in our country.

Key words: artificial intelligence, digital economy, digital transformation, modernization, Big Data, Internet of things.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada sun'iy intellektning raqamli transformatsiyadagi roli va xususiyatlari, sun'iy intellekt sohasidagi rivojlanish tendentsiyalari, turli mamlakatlarda sun'iy intellekt sohasidagi ishlarning asosiy yo'nalishlari to'g'risidagi dunyoning etakchi olimlarining fikrlari o'rganiladi. o'zgarishlarda sun'iy intellektning o'rni bo'yicha asoslantirilgan xulosa va takliflar ishlab chiqilib, uni mamlakatimizda qo'llash bo'yicha tavsiyalar berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, raqamli iqtisodiyot, raqamli transformatsiya, modernizatsiya, Big Data, Internet narsalar.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены мнения ведущих ученых мира о роли и характеристиках искусственного интеллекта в цифровой трансформации, проанализированы тенденции развития в области искусственного интеллекта, основные направления работ в области искусственного интеллекта в разных странах мира. Также выработаны обоснованные выводы и предложения о роли искусственного интеллекта в трансформации, даны рекомендации по его применению в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, цифровая экономика, цифровая трансформация, модернизация, большое количество данных, интернет вещей.

INTRODUCTION

We all know that today digital technologies have such a great impact on our lives that it is difficult to imagine not only our daily lives but also the development of socio-economic spheres without them. As the world develops, of course, the introduction of smart technologies into the activities of every industry makes a great contribution to the radical change of this industry. Due to the rapid development of technologies, what was in demand yesterday is losing its importance today. A saturated market, high competition, and customer demands are some of the reasons for the demand for digital transformation in the economy. Introducing new technologies and artificial intelligence is one of the biggest challenges today. On the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, "dated January 28, 2022, No. PF-60, by actively introducing "Green Economy" technologies in all sectors, issues of taking measures to increase the energy efficiency of the economy by 20% and reduce the amount of harmful gases released into the air by 20% have been determined. In this regard, the use of artificial intelligence acts as a "catalyst" in accelerating the digitization of economic sectors in the country ^[1]. At the same time, it creates the groundwork for the creation of highly innovative technologies.

In Uzbekistan, the development of information technology and the digital economy is set to take place among the leading countries with innovative development by 2030, which is a priority task. It should be noted that in the "Year of Development of Science, Enlightenment, and Digital Economy," significant changes in information technologies and digitization were implemented, and a number of important programs were adopted. In particular, the decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the widespread introduction of digital economy and electronic government" and "On additional measures to automate the procedures for providing public social services and assistance to the population" and other regulatory legal documents in our country aim at accelerating digitalization and the introduction of modern technologies in socio-economic spheres ^[2].

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the process of analyzing the literature on the topic, we witnessed that several leading economists and specialists conducted scientific research on the development of artificial intelligence in digital transformation, which is as follows: For example, in Uzbekistan, problems of artificial intelligence, as well as models and methods of implementation of the digital economy and information technologies, have been implemented in a number of scientific works. According to N.V. Gorodnova, the introduction of artificial intelligence algorithms as an assistant with additional capabilities into human life allows us to get the main advantage of such integration, which is based on the fact that it not only speeds up the decision-making process but also significantly improves its quality ^[3].

L.I. According to the analysis by Arkhipov, in 2018, the amount of income from the use of big data and business analytics services in the world was 168.8 billion US dollars, and according to the forecast, this figure will exceed 274.3 billion US dollars by the end of 2022 ^[4].

V.V. Zhilin and O.A. Safaryan's research revealed that 37 percent of companies today use algorithmic services and artificial intelligence technologies, which indicates that the possibilities of using new high-intelligence technologies will continue to increase in the future ^[5].

It was believed that this value is created only in the production sector; non-production (science, culture, health, finance, passenger transport, defense, and other sectors) is only consumed.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the digital transformation, economic research methods such as studying the research conducted by world scientists and economists on the development of artificial intelligence, collecting data, analyzing the collected data, synthesizing, and logical thinking were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

As we know, today, in the conditions of international globalization, the whole world recognizes that a new stage of economic development is being reached directly due to the development of the digital economy and artificial intelligence. It is also known from international experience that the digitization of the economy should be emphasized as an important criterion for ensuring socio-economic stability in many ways. At this point, it should be noted that in the future, there will be no development or growth without a digital economy; therefore, with a deep understanding of this issue, it is necessary to strengthen research only from a scientific-theoretical and practical point of view. First of all, it is permissible to dwell on the essence of the concept of the digital economy as an economic category and its application features. So, nowadays, there are different approaches to the concept of the digital economy.

Due to the digital transformations taking place in modern reality, the emergence and use of new technologies are increasing. All areas of business and social life are introduced by intelligent systems that can work effectively in a dynamically changing world. The digital economy is the basis of the entire government system, economy, new business models, and the fourth industrial revolution. AI technology has been researched for more than half a century. During the development of this field of science, the interest in such a promising direction in the IT field varied depending on scientific achievements and the development of practical areas of application of artificial intelligence. Over the past 10 years, many important advances have been made in improving the components of this technology, and the IT market has identified new possible uses for AI. Business entities should use this tool to maintain competitiveness and develop their own subsystems, which will encourage countries to join the technological race in order to stimulate the economy, strengthen their geopolitical position, and improve the standard of living of the population.

In addition to its direct use in production, the use of artificial intelligence in logistics allows for real-time fleet management while significantly reducing fuel consumption and other costs. AI can also reduce energy consumption in data centers. In addition, AI can help with digital security. For example, software firm Pivotal has created an AI system that can detect when text is likely to be part of a password and randomly generate passwords online. Meanwhile, Lex Machina is mixing AI and data analytics to revolutionize patent litigation. Many social bot startups automate tasks like meeting scheduling, business information and data retrieval, and expense management.

Signs of the digital economy are a high degree of automation, electronic document exchange, electronic integration of accounting and management systems, electronic databases, the availability of SRM (customer relationship management), and corporate networks. In the digital economy, costs for payments are reduced (for example, travel to the bank and other resources are saved), more and faster information is obtained about goods and services, opportunities for goods and services to enter the global market in the digital world are

greater, and feedback (desire) Goods and services are rapidly improved due to the rapid acquisition of the opinion of the farmer. Although digital data is a valuable economic resource, it is only useful when it is transformed into a digital mindset. With the advent of the digital economy comes the challenge of creating digital platforms and monetizing the rapidly growing digital data. It is important to identify the ways to create value and the means to eliminate obstacles in these processes. It provides an understanding of the potential for value creation and distribution, value renewal, value management, and value capture. In the further perspective of modern development, technologies for processing large-scale data (Big Data), artificial intelligence, neuro-technologies, quantum technologies, the Internet of Things, robotics and sensors, digital electronic platforms, cloud and mobile technologies, virtual and augmented reality technologies, digital technologies such as crowd-sourcing, blockchain technologies, cryptocurrencies, and 3D technologies are becoming crucial.

Figure 1: The main reasons why different sectors of the economy have not been digitally transformed¹

By knowing the main directions of work in the field of artificial intelligence in different countries around the world, it is possible to determine the development trends of artificial intelligence. The lines of work show us which are currently most in demand or most promising for achieving results. These works are focused in the following directions:

1. Deep learning's goal is to minimize the training time of the neural network and reduce the required size of the training sample; ideally, the neural network should be trained in real time.
2. Development of neuromorphic microcircuits and neurocomputers. Neurocomputers are a new type of computer. They have high performance due to parallel data processing and high reliability due to the exchange of nodes (i.e., neurons) and the presence of a large number of connections between them. An artificial neural network can be transferred from one neurocomputer to another, like a computer program.
3. Development of neurocomputer interfaces. Neural interfaces are devices for direct information exchange between the human brain and a computer, enabling hybrid human-machine intelligence to emerge in the future.
4. Development of unmanned vehicles (and computer vision). Introduction of unmanned vehicles into everyday life.
5. Improvement of speech recognition systems.
6. Complexity of robots. The robot must read and learn the incoming data with its own knowledge base. The study of the group behavior systems of robots and the interaction of robots with humans in performing any operations for the efficient distribution of tasks between them.

Further personalization of services is possible if, based on the available data on the user's behavior model, an application with artificial intelligence can ideally offer a service suitable for him in a particular situation, etc.

¹ <https://www.kpi.com/uz/digital-transformation-basic-strategies-for-your-business/>

Based on the above promising directions of development in the field of artificial intelligence, we can draw conclusions about the general trends in the development and application of artificial intelligence. The main development trends can be named as follows:

The first trend. Expanding the computing and functional capabilities of artificial intelligence (as a result of increasing the computing power of software and hardware systems, including the use of distributed architecture for graphics processors and computing systems).

The second trend is the development of robotic services with the help of artificial intelligence to get rid of the influence of the “human factor” and free people from monotonous work.

It involves the development of autonomous agents to which the user can delegate certain tasks.

The third trend. The growth of the artificial intelligence technology market is fueled by machine learning and data analysis technologies.

Digital transformation leads to economic growth and new opportunities. First, by automating the processes, it provides an opportunity to store all data in one place and process it by the system, which reduces the impact of the human factor. Secondly, due to process optimization, there will be time and opportunities to introduce and develop innovations. This is an investment in the future. In addition, there is the availability of large amounts of information for education. Today, due to this factor, various tools—in particular, simple and cheap tools for data storage and processing—and various algorithms have been created. But everything has a downside. The radical change will lead to a shortage of people who can help manage the processes, and according to McKinsey, automation could lead to the loss of 73 million workers in the US and more than 120 million in India by 2030.

Within the framework of the concept of socio-economic complex development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, improvement of the financing system of enterprises of the real sector of the economy, development of the leading sectors of the country’s economic growth in the medium and long term aimed at implementing the priority directions of the development of the real sector of the economy, further increasing their economic efficiency by reducing the level of resource consumption, transferring the economy from a producer of raw materials and semi-finished products based on medium-level technology to a producer of finished products, introducing the requirements of the green economy into practice, rationally using the existing potential of the tourism sector. The task of improving the infrastructure to turn the republic into a tourism center in the region is one of the priority strategic tasks.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

It can be seen that, over the years, the use of artificial intelligence technologies has been effective for the development of the country. It should be noted that these technologies play an important role not only in economic spheres but also in the lives of society. Year by year, artificial intelligence technologies are becoming a part of our lives and are the main impetus for development.

In conclusion, it can be said that every country should widely use artificial intelligence technologies to maintain its position in the world and to rise to the top. In order for our country to prosper in the future and for the next generation to use these technologies correctly and wisely, we should take action now, pay attention to the development of artificial intelligence technologies, and reduce their harm.

Reference:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” dated January 28, 2022, No. 60. – <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>.
2. Resolution No. 4699, dated April 28, 2020, of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, “On measures for wide implementation of the digital economy and electronic government”.
3. Городнова Н.В. Применение искусственного интеллекта в экономической дипломатии и международной торговле // Вопросы инновационной экономики. – 2021. – № 2. – doi: 10.18334/vines.11.2.112214.
4. Архипов Л.И. Большие данные и искусственный интеллект в бизнесе: развитие и регулирование // Big Data and Advanced Analytics. – 2020. – № 6-3. – с. 122- 127.
5. Жилин В.В., Сафарьян О.А. Искусственный интеллект в системах хранения данных // Вестник Донского государственного технического университета. – 2020. – № 2. – с. 196-200. – doi: 10.23947/1992-5980-2020-20-2-196-200.
6. Бабич В.Н., Кириллова Е.А. Обзор отдельных вопросов и области больших данных и искусственного интеллект. - М.: ФКУ “ГИАЦ МВД России, 2019. – 148 с. “Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar” (Economics and Innovative Technologies) ilmiy elektron jurnali 338 <http://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz>
7. <https://www.kpi.com/uz/raqamli-transformatsiya-biznesingiz-uchun-asosiy-strategiyalar>.
8. under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Statistics Agency data.

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2024. № 4

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

